

Title. Predictive value of Doppler ultrasound-detected synovitis in relation to failed tapering of biology therapy in patients with rheumatoid arthritis.

Authors. Esperanza Naredo, Lara Valor, Inmaculada De la Torre, María Montoro, Natalia Bello, Julia Martínez-Barrio, Lina Martínez-Estupiñán, Juan Carlos Nieto, Juan Gabriel Ovalles-Bonilla, Diana Hernández-Flórez, Carlos M. González, Francisco Javier López-Longo, Indalecio Monteagudo, Luis Carreño.

Affiliation

Department of Rheumatology, Hospital General Universitario Gregorio Marañón, Faculty of Medicine, Universidad Complutense. Madrid, Spain.

Address reprint requests to Esperanza Naredo, MD. Department of Rheumatology. Hospital General Universitario Gregorio Marañón. Doctor Alvarez Sierra 4, 4º A, 28033 Madrid, Spain. E-mail: enaredo@ser.es

Short title. Doppler ultrasound in biologic therapy tapering

Author contributions

Study design. Esperanza Naredo, Lara Valor, Inmaculada De la Torre, María Montoro, Luis Carreño.

Acquisition of data. Esperanza Naredo, Lara Valor, Inmaculada De la Torre, María Montoro, Natalia Bello, Julia Martínez-Barrio, Lina Martínez-Estupiñán, Juan Carlos Nieto, Juan Gabriel Ovalles-Bonilla, Diana Hernández-Flórez, Carlos M. González, Francisco Javier López-Longo, Indalecio Monteagudo.

Analysis and interpretation of data. Esperanza Naredo, Lara Valor, Inmaculada De la Torre, María Montoro, Luis Carreño.

Manuscript preparation. Esperanza Naredo, Luis Carreño.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: To investigate the predictive value of synovitis detected by Doppler ultrasound (DUS) in relation to failed tapering of biologic therapy (BT) in rheumatoid arthritis (RA) patients in sustained clinical remission.

Methods: Seventy-seven RA patients (52 women, 25 men) in sustained clinical remission, treated with stable dosage of BT were prospectively recruited. BT was tapered according to an agreed strategy implemented in clinical practice (i.e. increasing the interval between doses for subcutaneous BT and reducing the dose for intravenous BT). BT tapering failure was assessed at 6 and 12 months. DUS investigation of 42 joints for the presence and grade (0-3) of B-mode synovial hypertrophy and synovial power Doppler (PD) signal (i.e. Doppler synovitis) was performed at baseline by a rheumatologist blinded to clinical and laboratory data. Hand and foot radiographs were obtained at baseline and at 12-month followup.

Results: Forty-six (59.7%) patients were on subcutaneous BT and 31 (40.3%) on intravenous BT. Thirty-five (45.5%) patients presented BT tapering failure at 12 months, 23 of them (29.9% of all patients) in the first 6 months of BT tapering. In logistic regression analysis the baseline Disease Activity Score (DAS) 28 and the global score of Doppler synovitis were identified as independent predictors of BT tapering failure at 12 and 6 months. The presence of Doppler synovitis was the strongest predictor for BT tapering failure. No patient showed radiographic progression.

Conclusions: Our results suggested that the presence of Doppler-detected synovitis may predict BT tapering failure in RA patients in sustained clinical remission.

Key-words. Ultrasound, Doppler, synovitis, rheumatoid arthritis, biologic therapy

INTRODUCTION

The high economic impact of biologic therapy (BT) on healthcare systems has promoted, in recent years, a great interest in optimizing BT by either withdrawing or tapering these drugs in rheumatoid arthritis (RA) patients in sustained clinical remission (1,2).

Several studies have shown the capability of ultrasound (US) to detect B-mode synovitis and synovial Doppler activity in a high percentage of RA patients in clinical remission treated with either synthetic or biological disease modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) (3-7). However, the most important capability aspect is that US-detected subclinical synovitis, mainly synovial Doppler signal, has shown predictive value in relation to both radiographic damage progression (8,9) and disease flare or relapse (5,9,10).

The primary objective of this prospective observational longitudinal study was to investigate the predictive value of synovitis detected by Doppler US (DUS) in relation to failed tapering of BT at 6 and 12 months in RA patients in sustained clinical remission. The secondary objectives were as follows: 1) To investigate the predictive value of clinical and laboratory biomarkers in relation to failed tapering of BT at 6 and 12 months in these patients; 2) To establish the minimal joint count that should be assessed by DUS to discriminate between RA patient with successful BT tapering and BT tapering failure at 6 and 12 months.

METHODS

Patients

Eighty consecutive RA patients [54 women, 26 men] (11), treated with BT were prospectively recruited from the Biologic Therapy Unit of our center. Inclusion criteria

were the following: 1) Being in sustained clinical remission judged by their usual consultant rheumatologist in clinical visits every 3 months in the previous 12 months and being in remission according to either the Disease Activity Score in 28 joints (DAS28) criterion [i.e. DAS28 < 2.6] or the Simplified Disease Activity Index (SDAI) criterion [i.e. SDAI < 3.3] and in remission or low disease activity [i.e. DAS28 < 3.2; SDAI < 11] according to the other criterion at baseline; 2) Being in treatment with stable dosage of BT and, if administered, with stable dosage of synthetic DMARDs at least in the previous 6 months; 3) Being in treatment with ≤ 5 mg/day of prednisone in the previous 6 months; 4) Having received neither nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs for more than 1 week nor local corticosteroid injections in the previous 6 months. Patients treated with rituximab were not included.

At inclusion, patients could receive either full dosage (i.e. labeled dosage) or tapered dosage of BT according to a one-step BT tapering strategy (i.e. increase of 50% in the interval between doses for subcutaneous BT or reduction of 25% of the dose for intravenous BT) implemented in clinical practice in our center before the study (12). The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the local ethics committee of the Hospital GU Gregorio Marañón (Madrid, Spain). Informed consent was obtained from all patients before study enrollment.

BT tapering strategy

In patients on full dosage, BT was tapered at baseline according to the BT tapering strategy previously implemented in our center (Table 1). At 6 months, BT was tapered again in patients who had not needed BT, synthetic DMARD or systemic corticosteroids dosage increase from baseline and were in remission according to either the DAS28 or the SDAI criterion and in remission or low disease activity according to the other criterion

(Table 1). In patients with tapered dosage prior to the study, BT was tapered only at baseline according to the strategy applied to the labeled-dosage patients at 6-months.

Clinical, laboratory, and radiographic assessment

Patient demographics and RA features were recorded at study entry. A standardized clinical and laboratory assessment was performed at baseline, at 6 and 12 months by two of the investigators (IDLT, LV) who were not the patients' consultant rheumatologists and were not involved in therapeutic decisions except baseline and 6-month BT tapering strategy. These investigators were blinded to the DUS findings. At each visit, patients were evaluated for disease activity according to the DAS28 and SDAI criteria. During the study period, the patients were routinely assessed by their consultant rheumatologists every 3 months and at any time in-between the clinical visits in cases of RA worsening. Therapeutic decisions between the standardized assessments were taken by the patients' consultant rheumatologist, according to their clinical practice, without knowledge of the DUS findings.

Radiographs of the patients' hands and feet were obtained at baseline and at 12-month. The radiographs were read by an independent investigator (NB) using the van der Heijde and colleagues' modification of the Sharp method (13) (See supplementary data).

DUS assessment

The patients underwent a baseline US assessment consisted of a systematic examination on B-mode and power Doppler (PD) mode of 36 joint regions (42 joints) according to a described standardised scanning technique (7,14). This assessment was performed by a rheumatologist experienced in musculoskeletal US (EN) who was unaware of the clinical, laboratory, and radiographic findings and was not involved in the treatment decisions.

The following bilateral joints/joint regions were investigated for the presence of intra-articular B-mode synovial hypertrophy (SH) and synovial PD signal: glenohumeral (i.e. posterior and axillary recesses and biceps sheath), elbow (i.e. anterior and posterior recesses), wrist (i.e. radiocarpal, midcarpal, and distal radioulnar joints, dorsal recesses), second through fifth metacarpophalangeal (MCP) (i.e. dorsal and palmar recesses), second through fifth proximal interphalangeal (PIP) of the hands (i.e. dorsal and palmar recesses), hip (i.e. anterior recess), knee (i.e. suprapatellar and parapatellar recesses), ankle joints (i.e. tibiotalar joint, dorsal recess and subtalar joint, medial and lateral recesses), and second through fifth metatarsophalangeal (MTP) joints (i.e. dorsal recess). These joints were investigated for the presence and score [0-3] of intra-articular B-mode synovial hypertrophy (SH) and synovial PD signal, according to the Outcome Measures in Rheumatology Clinical Trials (OMERACT) definitions (15) and published scoring systems (7,14), using a real-time scanner (Mylab 70 XVG, Esaote, Genoa, Italy) equipped with two multifrequency linear array transducers, a 6-18 MHz transducer for superficial areas and a 4-13 MHz transducer for deep areas. B-mode and PD machine settings were optimized before the study and standardized for the whole study. These settings were as follows: B-mode frequency of 10-18 MHz, B-mode gain of 56-62%, Doppler frequency of 6.3-14.3 MHz, Doppler gain of 45-62%, low-wall filters, and pulse repetition frequency of 500-750 Hz, depending on the depth of the anatomic area.

At each intra-articular synovial recess, SH was scored semiquantitatively on a scale of 0-3 (0, absent; 1, mild; 2, moderate; 3, marked). Synovial PD signal was also scored on a semiquantitative scale of 0-3 (0, no synovial PD signal; 1, mild [≤ 3 PD signals within the SH]; 2, moderate [> 3 PD signals in less than half of the SH]; 3, marked [PD signals in more than half of the SH]). Each joint/joint region was scored for B-mode SH and synovial PD signal on a scale from 0 to 3. These scores corresponded to the

maximum score for SH and PD signal, respectively, obtained from any one of the synovial sites (i.e. recess or joint) evaluated at each joint/joint region.

A global index for SH (SHI) [the sum of the SH scores obtained for each evaluated joint/joint region; 0-108] and a global index for Doppler synovitis (DSI) [the sum of synovial PD signal scores obtained for each evaluated joint/joint region; 0-108] were calculated for each patient. In addition, we calculated SHI and DSI for a 12-joint DUS scoring model (14) and a wrist-MCP-ankle-MTP DUS scoring model (7). The 12-joint DUS scoring model included bilateral elbow, wrist, second and third MCP joints, knee and ankle joints. The wrist-MCP-ankle-MTP DUS scoring model included 20 joint regions as follows: bilateral wrist, second through fifth MCP joints, ankle, and second through fifth MTP joints.

BT tapering failure criteria

BT tapering failure was assessed at the 6-month and 12-month standardized assessment. and was defined as 1) a reinstatement of pre-inclusion BT dosage or previous step dosage according to the time or an increase in synthetic DMARD dosage or systemic corticosteroid dosage ≥ 5 mg/day of prednisone by their usual consultant rheumatologist during the followup period or 2) the presence of non-remission disease according to both DAS28 (i.e. $\text{DAS28} \geq 2.6$) and SDAI (i.e. $\text{SDAI} \geq 3.3$) criteria and/or the presence of moderate or high disease activity according to either DAS28 (i.e. $\text{DAS28} \geq 3.2$) or SDAI (i.e. $\text{SDAI} \geq 11$) criterion .The time to BT tapering failure was recorded. In patients who fulfilled the second criterion of failure BT pre-inclusion dosage or previous step dosage were reinstated. Peri or intra-articular steroid injections were not considered failure but were recorded.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS, version 15.0 (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Comparison between two independent groups were analyzed using the T-test or the Man-Whitney test for quantitative variables, depending on the assumption of normality, and the Fisher exact test was used for qualitative variables.

Multivariate logistic regression was used to identify from among all baseline clinical, laboratory and DUS variables independent predictors of BT tapering failure at 6 and 12 months. Only variables reaching a p-value lower than 0.10 in bivariate models were used in multivariate models. Forced introduction as well as forward and backward stepwise procedures were used for variable selection. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were used to determine the best cutoff value to classify patients as BT tapering success/failure for quantitative variables retained in the final models. P-values < 0.05 were considered significant.

RESULTS

Demographics and baseline data

The data from 77 patients [52 women, 25 men; mean (SD, range) age, 58.2 (13.1, 25-86) years] who completed the study were analyzed. Three patients dropped out of the study within 3 months after inclusion due to BT withdrawal because of infection, stroke and patient's desire, respectively. The mean (SD, range) disease duration was 13.1 (6.8, 3-31) years. The mean (SD, range) remission duration at baseline was 35.7 (28.4, 12-144) months. Forty-six (59.7%) patients were on subcutaneous BT and 31 (40.3%) on intravenous BT. Twenty-three (29.9%) patients were treated with adalimumab, 21 (27.3%) with etanercept, 18 (23.4%) with infliximab, 7 (9.1%) with tocilizumab, 6 (7.8%) with abatacept, and 2 (2.6%) with golimumab. At inclusion, 59 (76.6%) patients were on labeled dosage of BT. Forty-seven (61%) patients were taking a concomitant synthetic

DMARD, most of them (80.9%) methotrexate. Nine patients (11.7%) were taking oral prednisone (≤ 5 mg/day).

Baseline DAS28 criterion of remission was fulfilled in 77 (100%) patients and SDAI criterion of remission was fulfilled in 51 (66.2%) patients. The mean (SD, range) DAS28 was 1.82 (0.61, 0.49-2.58) and the mean (SD, range) SDAI was 2.55 (2.33, 0.1-8.2). The mean (SD, range) baseline total radiographic score was 43.0 (43.9, 2-205).

At baseline, 73 (94.8%) patients showed a SHI > 0 and 26 (33.8%) patients showed a DSI > 0 . The mean (SD, range) SHI was 6.36 (5.05, 0-22) and the mean (SD, range) DSI was 1.13 (2.05, 0-11). A representative DUS images of synovitis in a RA patients in clinical remission on BT is shown in supplementary Figures S1.

BT tapering failure

Thirty-five (45.5%) patients [14 (30.4%) patients on subcutaneous BT and 21 (67.7%) patients on intravenous BT; 29 (49.2%) patients on BT full dosage at baseline and 6 (33.3%) patients on BT tapered dosage at baseline] presented BT tapering failure within the 12-month followup, 23 of them (29.9% of all patients) in the first 6 months of BT tapering. The patients with tapering failure during the follow up period were on the following therapies; 5 (14.3%) patients on adalimumab, 9 (25.7%) on etanercept, 12 (34.7) on infliximab, 7 (20%) on tocilizumab, and 2 (5.7%) on abatacept.

Of the 23 patients who had BT tapering failure at 6 months, in 14 (60.9%) the pre-inclusion dosage of BT had been reinstated by their usual consultant rheumatologist because of disease activity worsening at a mean (SD, range) of 4 (1.5, 1-6) months since baseline and 9 (39.1%) met the DAS/SDAI-determined failure criteria at the 6 month assessment. Of the 12 patients who had BT tapering failure between 6 and 12 months, in 11 (91.7%) the previous step dosage of BT had been reinstated by their usual consultant

rheumatologist at a mean (SD, range) of 10.9 (1.3, 8-12) months since baseline and 1 (8.3%) fulfilled the DAS/SDAI-determined failure criteria at the 12 month assessment.

Three (3.9%) patients required an intra-articular steroid injection during the followup, 2 of them in addition fulfilled tapering failure criteria while in 1 patient BT was successfully tapered at 12 months.

Comparison between patients with successful and failed BT tapering at 12 and 6 months

Table 2 displays the baseline clinical, laboratory, and DUS parameters in patients with successful and failed BT tapering. Patients who presented BT tapering failure had significantly longer disease duration, a greater number of synthetic DMARDs, and a higher baseline DAS28 and SDAI than patients with successful BT tapering at 6 and 12 months. All baseline Doppler variables were significantly higher in patients with BT tapering failure as compared to patients with BT tapering success at 6 and 12 months. Baseline and final radiographs were available for 62 (80.5%) patients; 58 (93.5%) of them showed erosions at baseline. No patient showed radiographic progression.

Predictor factors of BT tapering failure

In logistic regression analysis the baseline DAS28 and DSI for the 42-joint, 12-joint and wrist-MCP-ankle-MTP DUS assessments were identified as independent predictors of BT tapering failure at 6 and 12 months in both the total population and the group who received labeled-dosage BT at baseline. These variables were dichotomized using ROC curves. The cutoff values for baseline DAS28 and DSI that showed the highest sensitivity and specificity for BT tapering outcome were 2.2 and 0.5, respectively. Table

3 shows the OR with 95% CI for BT tapering failure for these variables in the final multivariate logistic models. The presence of Doppler synovitis was the strongest predictor for BT tapering failure in all models.

The odds and probability of BT tapering failure at 6 and 12 months for combined dichotomized baseline DAS28 and DSI in the total population and in the labeled-dosage group are shown in Table 4. Neither B-mode variables nor the remaining clinical and laboratory variables reached statistical significance in the multiple regression analysis at 6 or 12 months.

DISCUSSION

In our study population 45.5% of patients presented BT tapering failure at 12 months 65.7% of them in the first 6 months of followup. Overall, our results seem relatively similar or little poorer than those from some other studies on BT tapering (16-18). In accordance with previously published data, we did not find radiographic structural progression at 12 months despite clinical failure (19). Nevertheless, longer time assessment of radiographic progression should confirm this finding.

Of particular note was that in our study, most importantly the presence of Doppler synovitis in any studied joint but also the baseline DAS28 were strongly associated with BT tapering failure both at 6 and 12 months. Recently, Iwamoto et al (20) reported a significant association between disease relapse at 6 months (42.5% of patients) and the baseline PD synovitis score in 42 patients with established RA in DAS28-determined remission who discontinued BT. Conversely, we did not find other predictors among demographics, RA or treatment characteristics. Our results suggested that before considering BT tapering in RA patients in sustained clinical remission, preferably with a low DAS28, a DUS assessment may be highly useful in confirming the absence of Doppler synovitis to enhance the appropriateness of patient selection for this therapeutic

decision. Our results also suggested that a reduced DUS assessment may be a feasible valid option for this strategy.

Some limitations in our study should be mentioned. The RA population was relatively small and very heterogeneous regarding RA characteristics and biologic agent and dosage. However, this was an observational study based on real clinical practice at our center where a non-evidence-based one-step tapering strategy had been previously implemented. In conclusion, we propose that DUS may contribute in improving the appropriate selection for BT tapering among RA patients in sustained clinical remission. Further studies on other RA populations are warranted to confirm these results.

Key messages

Doppler ultrasound predicted biologic therapy tapering failure in RA patients.

Doppler ultrasound may contribute in improving the appropriate selection for BT tapering among RA patients.

Conflict of interest statement

Esperanza Naredo has received speaker fees from Abbvie, Roche Farma, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Pfizer, UCB, General Electric Healthcare, and Esaote. Esperanza Naredo has received research funding from MSD.

Lara. Valor has received speaker fees from Abbvie, Roche Farma, Bristol-Myers Squibb and Pfizer.

Inmaculada De la Torre has received speaker fees from Abbvie, Roche Farma and Pfizer.

Juan Carlos Nieto-González has received speaker fees from Abbvie, Roche Farma, Pfizer, MSD.

Francisco Javier López-Longo has received speaker fees from Abbvie, Roche Farma, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Pfizer, UCB, MSD, Actelion. Francisco Javier López Longo has received research funding from Abbvie and GSK.

Indalecio Monteagudo has received speaker fees from Abbvie, Roche Farma, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Pfizer, UCB.

Funding statement. Supported by a grant from Fondo de Investigaciones Sanitarias (FIS), Instituto de Salud Carlos III, Madrid, Spain

REFERENCES

1. Yoshida K, Sung YK, Kavanaugh A, et al. Biologic discontinuation studies: a systematic review of methods. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2014;73:595-9.

2. Smolen JS, Landewe R, Breedveld FC, et al. EULAR recommendations for the management of rheumatoid arthritis with synthetic and biological disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs: 2013 update. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2014;73:492-509.
- 3.. Brown AK, Quinn MA, Karim Z, et al. Presence of significant synovitis in rheumatoid arthritis patients with disease-modifying antirheumatic drug-induced clinical remission: evidence from an imaging study may explain structural progression. *Arthritis Rheum* 2006;54:3761-73.
4. Saleem B, Brown AK, Keen H, et al. Disease remission state in patients treated with the combination of tumor necrosis factor blockade and methotrexate or with disease modifying antirheumatic drugs: A clinical and imaging comparative study. *Arthritis Rheum* 2009;60:1915-22.
5. Scire CA, Montecucco C, Codullo V, Epis O, Todoerti M, Caporali R. Ultrasonographic evaluation of joint involvement in early rheumatoid arthritis in clinical remission: power Doppler signal predicts short-term relapse. *Rheumatology* 2009;48:1092-7.
6. Balsa A, de Miguel E, Castillo C, Peiteado D, Martín-Mola E. Superiority of SDAI over DAS-28 in assessment of remission in rheumatoid arthritis patients using power Doppler ultrasonography as a gold standard. *Rheumatology* 2010;49:683-90.
7. Naredo E, Valor L, De la Torre I, et al. Ultrasound joint inflammation in rheumatoid arthritis in clinical remission: how many and which joints should be assessed? *Arthritis Care Res* 2013;65:512-7.
8. Brown AK, Conaghan PG, Karim Z, et al. An Explanation for the Apparent Dissociation Between Clinical Remission and Continued Structural Deterioration in Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 2008; 58: 2958-67.

9. Foltz V, Gandjbakhch F, Etchepare F, et al. Power Doppler Ultrasound, but Not Low-Field Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Predicts Relapse and Radiographic Disease Progression in Rheumatoid Arthritis Patients With Low Levels of Disease Activity. *Arthritis Rheum* 2012;64:67-76.
10. Saleem B, Brown AK, Quinn M, et al. Can flare be predicted in DMARD treated RA patients in remission, and is it important? A cohort study. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2012; 71:1316-21
11. Arnett FC, Edworthy SM, Bloch DA, et al. The American Rheumatism Association 1987 revised criteria for the classification of rheumatoid arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 1988; 31:315-24.
12. De La Torre I, Valor L, Nieto JC, Montoro M, Carreño L. Minimum Effective Dosages of Anti-TNF in Rheumatoid Arthritis: A Cross-sectional Study. *Reumatol Clin*. 2013 Nov doi: 10.1016/j.reuma.2013.07.009.
13. Van der Heijde DM. Assessment of radiographs in longitudinal observational studies. *J Rheumatol Suppl* 2004;69:46-7.
14. Naredo E, Rodríguez M, Campos C, et al. Validity, Reproducibility and Responsiveness of a 12-joint Simplified Power Doppler Ultrasonographic Assessment of Joint Inflammation in Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Arthritis Rheum* 2008;59:512-22.
15. Wakefield RJ, Balint P, Szkudlarek M, et al. Musculoskeletal Ultrasound Including Definitions for Ultrasonographic Pathology. *J Rheumatol* 2005;32:2485-7.
16. Smolen JS, Nash P, Durez P, et al. Maintenance, reduction, or withdrawal of etanercept after treatment with etanercept and methotrexate in patients with moderate rheumatoid arthritis (PRESERVE): a randomized controlled trial. *Lancet* 2013; 381: 918-29.

17. Van der Maas A, Kievit W, Van den Bemt BJJ, van den Hoogen FH, van Riel PL, den Broeder AA. Down-titration and discontinuation of infliximab in rheumatoid arthritis patients with stable low disease activity and stable treatment: an observational cohort study. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2012;71:1849-54.
18. Maneiro JR, Perez-Pampin E, Salgado E, Carmona L, Gomez-Reino JJ. Observational study of optimization of biologic therapies in rheumatoid arthritis: a single-centre experience. *Rheumatol Int* 2013 Jul 28.
19. Van den Broek M, Klarenbeek NB, Dirven L, et al. Discontinuation of infliximab and potential predictors of persistent low disease activity in patients with early rheumatoid arthritis and disease activity score-steered therapy: subanalysis of the BeSt study. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2011;70:1389-94.
20. Iwamoto T, Ikeda K, Hosokawa J, et al. Ultrasonographic assessment predicts relapse after discontinuation of biological agents in patients with rheumatoid arthritis in clinical remission. *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken)* 2014; Feb 10.

TABLES

Table 1. Biologic therapy tapering strategy

Biologic agent	Pre-inclusion dosage	Baseline tapering	6-month tapering
Adalimumab	40 mg /2 weeks	40 mg /21 days	40 mg /4 weeks
Etanercept	50 mg /week	50 mg /10 days	50 mg /2 weeks
Golimumab	50 mg /month	50 mg /45 days	50 mg /2 months
Abatacept	500 mg (weight < 60 kg), 750 mg (weight \geq 60 kg and \leq 100kg) or 1,000 mg (weight > 100 kg)/4 weeks	Reduction of 25% of the pre-inclusion dose	Reduction of 50% of the pre-inclusion dose
Infliximab	3-5 mg/kg/8 weeks	Reduction of 25% of the pre-inclusion dose	Reduction of 50% of the pre-inclusion dose
Tocilizumab	8 mg/kg/4 weeks	Reduction of 25% of the pre-inclusion dose	Reduction of 50% of the pre-inclusion dose

Table 2. Baseline clinical, laboratory, and DUS parameters in patients with successful and failed BT tapering at 6 and 12 months.

Baseline variables	Successful BT tapering at 6 months (n=54)	Failed BT tapering at 6 months (n=23)	p-values	Successful BT tapering at 12 months (n=42)	Failed BT tapering at 12 months (n=35)	p-values
Age (years), mean (SD)	58 (13.8)	58.6 (11.6)	0.853	56.6 (13.9)	60.1 (12)	0.247
Sex (women), n (%)	35 (67.3)	17 (32.7)	0.596	26 (50)	26 (50)	0.330
Disease duration (years), mean (SD)	11.9 (6.6)	15.8 (6.8)	0.020	11.2 (6.7)	15.3 (6.4)	0.009
Duration of clinical remission (months), mean (SD)	38.7 (31.6)	28.6 (17.4)	0.156	39.5 (34.7)	31 (17.5)	0.170
Time from symptom onset to synthetic DMARDs (months), mean (SD)	12.8 (23.6)	23.6 (34.2)	0.114	10.5 (23.5)	22.6 (30.7)	0.060
Duration of synthetic DMARD treatment (years), mean (SD)	11.3 (18.2)	11.3 (5.2)	0.994	9.3 (11.3)	13.7 (19.3)	0.222
Number of synthetic DMARDs, mean (SD)	1.8 (0.9)	2.3 (1)	0.049	1.6 (0.8)	2.3 (1)	0.003
Time from symptom onset to biologic DMARDs (months), mean (SD)	78.2 (72.5)	95.4 (64.6)	0.331	76.6 (77.3)	91.5 (60.9)	0.357
Number of biologic DMARDs, mean (SD)	1.4 (0.9)	1.7 (0.9)	0.371	1.4 (0.8)	1.7 (1)	0.233
Concomitant synthetic DMARD, n (%)	31 (66)	16 (34)	0.445	26 (55.3)	21 (44.7)	1.000
Concomitant corticosteroids, n (%)	4 (44.4)	5 (55.6)	0.117	2 (22.2)	7 (77.8)	0.071
Smokers, n (%)	9 (75)	3 (25)	1.000	5 (41.7)	7 (58.3)	0.362
DAS28 (0-9.4), mean (SD)	1.68 (0.57)	2.14 (0.58)	0.002	1.66 (0.60)	2.01 (0.56)	0.011

SDAI (0-86), mean (SD)	2.05 (2.06)	3.74 (2.54)	0.003	1.85 (2.08)	3.4 (2.37)	0.003
Positive RF, n (%)	24 (63.2)	14 (36.8)	0.220	17 (44.7)	21 (55.3)	0.111
Positive ACPA, n (%)	38 (67.9)	18 (32.1)	0.582	28 (50)	28 (50)	0.211
SHI (0-108), mean (SD)	6.4 (5.4)	6.2 (4.3)	0.831	5.7 (4.7)	7.2 (5.4)	0.187
DSI (0-108), mean (SD)	0.4 (1.2)	1.2 (1)	0.002	0.1 (0.5)	2.3 (2.5)	<0.0005
12-joint SHI (0-36), mean (SD)	3.3 (2.8)	4 (3)	0.370	2.9 (2.3)	4.3 (3.3)	0.028
12-joint DSI (0-36), mean (SD)	0.5 (1.5)	1.8 (1.8)	0.001	0.1 (0.2)	1.9 (2.1)	<0.0005
WMAM SHI (0-60), mean (SD)	4.2 (4.3)	4 (3)	0.837	4 (3.9)	4.4 (4)	0.646
WMAM DSI (0-60), mean (SD)	0.4 (1.6)	1.9 (1.5)	<0.0005	0.1 (0.5)	1.7 (2.2)	<0.0005

DUS, Doppler ultrasound; BT, biologic therapy; DMARDs, disease modifying antirheumatic drugs; DAS28, Disease Activity Score in 28 joints; SDAI, Simplified Disease Activity Index; RF, rheumatoid factor; ACPAs, anti-citrullinated peptide antibodies; SHI, global index for synovial hypertrophy; DSI, global index for Doppler synovitis; WMAM, wrist-metacarpophalangeal-ankle-metatarsophalangeal; SD, standard deviation.

Table 3. Multivariate logistic models for the total population and the labeled-dosage population.

	Model	Included variable	All patients				Baseline labeled-dosage patients			
			OR	95% CI (OR)		p-values	OR	95% CI (OR)		p-values
				Lower	Upper			Lower	Upper	
BT tapering failure	A	DSI > 0	13,91	3,44	56,29	< 0.0005	21,11	3,81	117,10	< 0.0005

		DAS28 \geq 2.2	11,27	2,79	45,54	0.001	11,70	2,13	64,30	0.005
	B	12-joint DSI > 0	13,33	3,28	54,19	< 0.0005	18,11	3,40	96,35	0.001
		DAS28 \geq 2.2	11,43	2,85	45,88	0.001	11,38	2,12	61,10	0.005
	C	WMAM DSI > 0	18,32	4,39	76,41	< 0.0005	27,08	4,92	149,10	< 0.0005
		DAS28 \geq 2.2	9,83	2,40	40,31	0.002	9,17	1,66	50,76	0.011
12 months	A	DSI > 0	29,92	6,81	131,40	< 0.0005	23,07	5,03	105,83	< 0.0005
		DAS28 \geq 2.2	5,81	1,62	20,93	0.007	3,79	0,95	15,13	0.059
	B	12-joint DSI > 0	42,86	7,91	232,34	< 0.0005	31,82	5,67	178,46	< 0.0005
		DAS28 \geq 2.2	6,25	1,72	22,69	0.005	4,02	0,99	16,29	0.051
	C	WMAM DSI > 0	29,32	5,79	148,47	< 0.0005	21,79	4,22	112,47	< 0.0005
		DAS28 \geq 2.2	4,19	1,25	14,04	0.020	2,54	0,69	9,31	0.159

BT, biologic therapy; DAS28, Disease Activity Score in 28 joints; DSI, global index for Doppler synovitis; WMAM, wrist-metacarpophalangeal-ankle-metatarsophalangeal; OR, odds ratios; CI, confidence interval.

Table 4. Odds and probability of failure at 12 and 6 months for combined dichotomized baseline DAS28 and SDI.

Baseline variables in all patients	Odds of BT tapering failure at 6 months	Odds of BT tapering failure at 12 months	Probability of BT tapering failure at 6 months	Probability of BT tapering failure at 12 months
DAS 28 < 2.2 + DSI =0	0.05	0.15	0.04	0.13
DAS 28 < 2.2 + DSI > 0	0.64	4.52	0.39	0.82
DAS 28 \geq 2.2 + DSI =0	0.52	0.88	0.34	0.47
DAS 28 \geq 2.2 + DSI > 0	7.21	26.02	0.88	0.96

Baseline variables in baseline labeled-dosage patients	Odds of BT tapering failure at 6 months	Odds of BT tapering failure at 12 months	Probability of BT tapering failure at 6 months	Probability of BT tapering failure at 12 months
DAS 28 < 2.2 + DSI =0	0.03	0.18	0.03	0.15
DAS 28 < 2.2 + DSI > 0	0.58	4.13	0.37	0.81
DAS 28 ≥ 2.2 + DSI =0	0.32	0.68	0.24	0.40
DAS 28 ≥ 2.2 + DSI > 0	6.80	15.66	0.87	0.94

BT, biologic therapy; DAS28, Disease Activity Score in 28 joints; DSI, global index for Doppler synovitis.